

MODERN REQUIREMENTS FOR THE ORGANIZATION OF MUSIC CLUBS IN GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS.

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Abstract. This article describes the organizational issues of musical clubs in general secondary schools. The article highlights the modern requirements for the organization of music clubs in general secondary schools and the important recommendations necessary for music teachers during their activities.

Key words: music, circle, classics, spirit, voice, folk songs, modern songs, classical music, range.

Scientific studies devoted to the problems of music pedagogy and aesthetic education show that the forms and methods of work in art circles are close to each other in many ways. They often complement and enrich each other even though they are oriented towards the same goal.

Singing clubs organized in general education schools should first of all have the goal of preparing students for certain artistic activities. Because today's schoolchildren are responsible for the education of the young generation in the future, and it is their responsibility to educate the young generation in an artistic and aesthetic way and to make them perfect people.

Singing clubs organized in general education schools familiarize students with national and modern songs and develop theoretical and practical skills and abilities to work in clubs.

Today's students are perfect and mature people of tomorrow, and all the knowledge and education given to them should include a number of vital and responsible tasks. One of the most important issues is their ideological, artistic and aesthetic education by widely involving them in certain fields of art. Artistic amateur circles are the most convenient and effective tool in this regard, and the activities in the circles have a strong impact on the formation of young people's minds, emotions, and future pedagogical skills and abilities.

The importance of music clubs is great in developing students' performance skills, nurturing and strengthening their voices, and developing their singing talents in all aspects.

Although many types of artistic amateurism have appeared in recent years, it is true that the art of singing remains the leader in terms of popularity. At the same time, it is gratifying that singing circles are organized mainly in general secondary schools, secondary specialized and higher educational institutions.

Acquainting young people with the art of our national singing, forming the right attitude and taste for songs created in imitation of artistically shallow, light-hearted, foreign music is one of the most urgent tasks for singing circles. That's why every lesson conducted in singing circles should teach young people to cultivate feelings of benevolence to beauty, positive events, to think of high artistic, sophisticated works and artistic shallow, superficial, fake works. This, in turn, develops their sense of taste, national sophistication, national ethics, national art of the people and the art of the peoples of the world.

Modern music cannot be understood without experiencing classical music. The fact that folk songs, which have been a part of the spiritual treasury of the people for several centuries and have been serving the education of several generations, are now somewhat neglected by young people, requires a radical improvement of their work in this regard. A. Novoiy, Lutfiy, Babur, Mashrab, Ogahiy, Zebuniso, Nadira, Uvaisiy, Haziniy, Furqat, Muqimiy, Mahtumquli and other classical poets who glorify country, country, homeland and parents, correctness, goodness, manners the eternal, popular, popular nature of the songs sung by many generations with their poems praising life and friendship actually make the poetic ideas in them very elegant, close to the spirit, heart, soul of the people It is in harmony with the musical tones that have been. The educational importance of such songs is self-evident.

Folklore songs related to the way of life and life traditions of our people are of incomparable importance in helping young people to know, feel and expand their imagination of the past life of our people.

It will be necessary to teach folk songs to young people in Ashula circles, and at the same time to teach them modern vocal, choral, pop songs that glorify our current life. After all, by teaching and performing songs on various topics, students enter the magical world and meaning of these songs, and with their performance, they also have an aesthetic effect on the people around them.

Singing clubs organized in general education schools should familiarize the teachers involved with the secrets of the art of singing and train them to become selfless propagandists of this art. Therefore, conducting group classes based on advanced methods and experiences with impressive, interesting, demonstrative materials ensures its effectiveness and increases students' interest in the art of singing.

The leaders of the club conduct the training with national and modern musical instruments, through technical means, i.e. by listening to the recordings of the songs of famous performers, giving interesting and necessary information about them, and then start learning in every way. 'will be a slave.

The leader of the circle has a great responsibility, he should have good musical and singing skills, as well as high qualifications and experience. The leader must carefully prepare for each exercise, draw up an outline plan for it. It is known that amateur students want to learn and sing songs faster. Some of them learn and sing songs on the Internet, audio devices, radio or television. The leader of the group examines each participant's voice capabilities in detail, advises them which songs to sing, which tone (curve) they can sing, and explains that singing the songs they come across in their own way can damage the vocal apparatus first of all, with them the art of singing will hold interesting conversations about the contributions of famous musicians, hafiz to the development of our national singing and music culture. This situation has a positive effect on the aesthetic education of students by expanding their imagination and understanding of our national singing.

Knowledge and understanding of the anatomy and physiology of the vocal apparatus, the theory and practice of singing (vocal performance) The interviews are important for them to become professional professionals. Students participating in singing clubs are also of different ages. It is natural that there are big differences between the voice characteristics and types of the participants of the circle. Also, some young people's voices may not have gone through the full mutation process. The leader should take all this into account and record it in a special notebook.

It is desirable that the repertoire of songs recommended to the participants of the circle should be in accordance with their age, vocal ability, and performance ability, should not be pleasant or sad, and should be educational as much as possible. Together with examples of folk art, it is necessary to have a place in the repertoire of composers' songs that praise the homeland, mother nature, hard work, human qualities, feelings, and pure love in folk melody and spirit. It should not be concluded that the work of the head of the circle is limited to this. In the course of the work, it is possible to carefully select and include in the repertoire of the circle songs that are broadcast on the Internet, audio devices, radio, television, and are suitable for the participants of the circle in all respects.

Folk songs intended for amateurs, samples of modern songs, choral works can be presented in the following order:

- for amateurs of the first group, songs of medium complexity are recommended. It included folk songs suitable for teenagers, as well as light amateur songs ranging from the I-octave C sound to the II-octave F-sol sound.

- the amateurs of the second group are introduced to the traditional performance samples, which have a wider range and the performer requires a certain level of performance skills and experience, as well as songs that are part of the status and can be learned and performed relatively easily.

In addition, the leader of the circle can independently choose songs based on the wishes and desires of the participants. In this regard, it is appropriate to compile new repertoires of songs using some sources and collections as a help to them.

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